

ZEB LABORATORY

Report 2024

Photo: Anne Jørgensen Bruland

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Foreword

NTNU and SINTEF are dedicated to advancing a zero-carbon society through innovative research and sustainable practices. Guided by their visions – NTNU’s “Knowledge for a better world” and SINTEF’s “Technology for a better society” – both institutions align closely with the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Together, they emphasize green, digital, and circular transitions to build a sustainable future by developing technologies and strategies that drive us toward a zero-carbon world.

A crucial focus within this transition is the role of cities, neighbourhoods, and buildings. By 2050, nearly 70% of the world’s population will reside in urban areas, with construction, buildings, and real estate already responsible for 40% of global greenhouse gas emissions – a figure that grows further when considering land use, mobility, and other climate-intensive activities. These pressures, along with the impact on biodiversity, make it essential to transform our built environments into active contributors to sustainability. This transformation requires buildings that not only incorporate sustainable materials and adaptable designs but also operate efficiently to maintain high indoor environmental quality, providing healthy and comfortable living spaces. Equally important is ensuring that buildings are resilient to climate impacts, with design considerations for future adaptability, reuse potential, and minimized resource consumption, making our built environments a proactive force in reducing emissions and enhancing urban sustainability.

Decades of partnership between NTNU and SINTEF in building research have provided significant insights and a robust foundation for tackling these challenges. However, much work remains, and

new tools and infrastructure for education and research are essential to accelerate progress. This is precisely why we conceived and funded, with additional support from the Research Council of Norway, the ZEB Laboratory to advance ambitious goals in sustainable built environment research. As detailed in the first part of this report, its design and development aimed to showcase the current state of knowledge, create a state-of-the-art facility for exploring innovative solutions, and demonstrate our commitment to research and collaboration with both industry and society.

Today, the ZEB Laboratory continues to receive foundational support from the owner institutions, as well as from project-based grants. These enable a wide range of research activities, which you will learn more about in this report. These research highlights demonstrate the unique capabilities of this infrastructure, which, coupled with joint efforts within our institutions and with external partners, make it possible to advance new insights, methods, technologies, and services that contribute to sustainable building practices.

We are convinced that through continued broad collaboration across NTNU-SINTEF’s network of our partner research institutions, industry, and society, we can address the significant challenges we face in the transition towards a more sustainable world. With a clear focus and a commitment to working closely, we will progress together on this path and create impactful knowledge through research.

We hope you find this Annual Report engaging and insightful.

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Photo: Nicola Lolli

ZEB Laboratory at a Glance

Purpose and ambition

The Zero Emission Building Laboratory (ZEB Laboratory), located at the NTNU Gløshaugen Campus in Trondheim, Norway, is one of the tools developed by NTNU and SINTEF to push the boundaries of sustainable architecture and zero-emission building technologies. The primary purpose of the ZEB Laboratory, jointly owned and operated by NTNU and SINTEF, is to serve as a research tool for developing and testing new

technologies and solutions for zero-emission buildings. However, the building fulfills other functions too: it is a demonstrator of innovative solutions in building design, energy efficiency, and environmental sustainability; it is a living laboratory and research testbed; and, last but not least, it is a state-of-the-art office and education building used daily by SINTEF's and NTNU's staff and students.

The design, construction, and operation of the ZEB Laboratory have been, and still are, an experiment in itself, aiming to demonstrate how it is possible to realize buildings with zero, or even negative, contributions of greenhouse gases during the life of the building. In its function as a demonstrator, the ZEB Laboratory is used to disseminate to a large audience how energy-efficient solutions and low-emission materials can be combined to create sustainable buildings. In addition to showcasing innovative solutions to industry partners and professional communities, it also provides a hands-on learning environment for students in architecture, engineering, and related fields. The facility is also meant to host workshops, seminars, and training and dissemination sessions, helping to educate the next generation of professionals in sustainable building design and construction.

The ZEB Laboratory is often visited by a larger audience of pupils, students, and the general public, and is used as a venue for events for the communication of science and technology, making it a unique tool for broad communication to society. In its function as a living laboratory and research testbed, it is used to conduct experimental investigations on various aspects of building performance, including energy use, indoor environmental quality, and user behavior. Researchers at the ZEB Laboratory study the interaction between building occupants and the built environment, aiming to develop strategies for improving comfort and reducing energy consumption.

One of the key research areas at the ZEB Laboratory is the evaluation of monitoring and control systems, and how data from operation can enhance the performance of the energy and environmental systems. The building's advanced monitoring systems record environmental data, energy demand, and renewable energy production, providing insights into the performance of zero-emission buildings and helping researchers and professionals design future solutions that minimize CO₂ emissions during building operation.

The Zero Emission Building Laboratory is a strategic research infrastructure of national and international relevance. The realization of the ZEB Laboratory has been possible thanks to the support of NTNU, SINTEF, Enova, and the Research Council of Norway through the National Financing Initiative for Research Infrastructure.

Photo: Matthias C. Herzog

Architecture and concept

The ZEB Laboratory is a four-story building with a total gross area of about 2000 m². Its design, based on research and development activities carried out in two Centres for Environment-friendly Energy Research, is characterized by a strong emphasis on the efficient use of energy and materials to realize one of the first buildings that do not contribute to greenhouse gas emissions during its entire life. The building has been conceived to reach the ZEB-COM target developed by the Research Centre on Zero Emission Buildings, which means neutral CO₂ emissions considering the materials, construction, and operation phases, over the life-time (60 years) of the building. Furthermore, it demonstrates climate change adaptation technologies, with a focus on building-related moisture proofing and innovative solutions for stormwater management. Several of the technologies and procedures addressing robustness against climate change were developed for the ZEB Laboratory in close collaboration with the Centre for Research-based Innovation Klima 2050.

The ZEB Laboratory is designed to be a flexible and adaptable space that can accommodate various research activities. The building includes office spaces (located on the 2nd and 3rd floors), teaching and dissemination areas (located on the 1st and 4th floors), and dedicated research and demonstration areas, with technical spaces for the installation and testing of building service systems. The 2nd floor hosts, as part of the office areas, two identical test rooms, equipped with specialized HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) systems, a large number of sensors, and high flexibility for control

systems. This set-up enables detailed studies on indoor environmental quality, energy use, and user interaction with the building, while the entire office and education areas of the building are equipped to enable longitudinal monitoring of energy flows, indoor climate, and user interaction with the spaces and equipment.

The layout of the building is designed to facilitate collaboration and interaction among researchers, students, and visitors. Open-plan office spaces and shared work areas are key features of this building, combining technical and functional needs in a way that supports open communication and knowledge exchange. The building also includes meeting rooms, seminar spaces, and a large cantina that serves as a main gathering point. About 70 researchers from different departments and groups in NTNU and SINTEF Community use the building as their office place.

The building's compact form and its orientation have been developed to maximize the exploitation of well-known strategies for energy-efficient buildings. The technical solutions adopted for

Emission balance for the ZEB Laboratory in a 60-year perspective.

the building envelope, both in terms of thermal insulation, window size and positions, movable screens, and solutions for solar shading, contribute to minimizing the use of energy for building climatization.

The building energy design combines thus an optimal exploitation of passive climatization strategies with low-exergy, highly efficient building services. The carefully designed integration of a hybrid ventilation system, combining automatically controlled windows with fully balanced mechanical ventilation, enhances optimal indoor air quality and energy efficiency.

The use of materials with low-embodied emissions and construction techniques that minimize material use and emissions in the construction phases further contribute to the building's low environmental impact. Technical solutions developed to tackle challenges induced by climate change and secure high energy performance and indoor environmental quality have been developed and implemented in this building. Facades and roofs are covered with solar PV panels, fully integrated into the visual identity of the building. This distinctive feature not only meets the energy supply needs of a zero-emission building but also gives it a unique architectural identity fully aligned with the ZEB-COM target and the climate adaptation focus.

Plan layout (1st floor to 4th floor) of the ZEB Laboratory

Design and construction process

Collaboration across disciplines, expertise, and above all, people, has been the key to ensuring that the ZEB Laboratory building meets its ambitious goals while maintaining flexibility for future research, education, and dissemination. The process behind the making of the ZEB Laboratory started with the idea to create a state-of-the-art building/laboratory and a successful pre-project application for a national research infrastructure to the Research Council of Norway submitted in 2012. The full project application was granted in 2015, and the design and process started soon after that.

One of the key aspects of the ZEB Laboratory's project was its delivery in line with the set ambitions (ZEB-COM), on time, and within budget. To reach this goal, the ZEB methodology was implemented in an innovative partnering contract as a project delivery model. The contractor organized the development of the project with a two-day start-up seminar, followed by co-location of the project team in Integrated Concurrent Engineering (ICE) regular sessions, which included gathering the project group in a physical "Big Room". The project team consisted of a group of people from the contractor, its team of designers and manufacturers, and people from the client's core group. This project enabled the developer to meet the project team one day a week to work through the project, drawing on input from all the technical and organizational participants involved. The participants worked

Project team members collaborate in the "Big Room" during an ICE session for the ZEB Laboratory. Photo: Tore Kvande

in themed technical groups and in plenum, and a series of ZEB workshops were held as part of the project process. Project participants and the developer established shared objectives and resolved their problems together. They evaluated the process and reached an understanding that it was mutual and concurrent iterations over time that generated value, helping the project to achieve its ZEB-related goals.

The project was managed through a series of target price controls which helped maintain

Structure of the Integrated Concurrent Engineering process for the ZEB Laboratory

financial discipline. This collaborative approach extended into the execution phase, with significant involvement from students in all phases, making the project a valuable educational experience. This is the first time that the ZEB methodology has been integrated into a collaborative effort of this type and with such extensive involvement of the client. The innovative nature of the project's execution model was followed closely by a doctoral candidate, who focused his research on this process. This model has thus been widely analyzed and documented, with extensive publication of experiences in scientific journals, user-oriented articles, and presentations.

Throughout the design and construction process, the ZEB-COM goal and climate adaptation focus behind the project have been central to a high number of teaching and education activities at NTNU. The building has also hosted numerous tours, with 1300 people visiting the construction site

before the COVID-19 pandemic halted such activities (i.e., the main bulk of visitors during nine months).

In the construction process, conscious efforts were made to involve apprentices, providing a critical learning environment for new technology, zero-emission building concepts, and climate adaptation strategies. Nineteen apprentices from various professions contributed to more than 20% of the total work hours, highlighting the project's commitment to education and skill development. The completed building continues to attract significant interest, with weekly visits from international groups and several tours delivered to different audiences every week.

In 2022, the ZEB Laboratory was awarded the highly recognized "State's Award for Building Quality" and the Bygg21's award for best practice "Betonghammeren".

Innovative technical solutions

Innovative technical solutions developed for the ZEB Laboratory can be clustered into four main categories: energy and environmental systems, climate adaptation and preparedness, building envelope and structure, and building monitoring and user interaction.

Energy and Environmental Systems

Wind and solar power are intermittent energy sources, necessitating solutions to reduce output peaks for heating by storing heat generated the previous day. A heat storage unit, or thermal battery, has been developed using bio-wax as the phase change material. This compact and efficient system responds rapidly to room heating peaks and can store heat for two to three days during the coldest periods. To the best of our knowledge, the ZEB Laboratory has been the first to implement this type of heat storage with bio-wax.

Energy-efficient climatization is important for both existing and future buildings. Ventilation systems must be energy efficient, have a small environmental footprint, and be flexible enough to adapt to various uses. A developed system enables a building to be climatized using natural forces, mechanical devices, or a combination of both. Each floor has its own dedicated ventilation system, with different methods of air supply tailored to specific needs.

Climate Adaptation and Preparedness

The ZEB Laboratory also demonstrates how buildings can adapt to climate change. Renewable energy generation using buildings often focuses on solar panels, which should also serve as roof cladding to reduce materials use. The laboratory features a 20-meter long, BIPV-installed, eaveless roof with highly efficient, rainproof, and ventilated solar panels. An interior guttering system maximizes the roof area for solar panels while preserving the building's architectural expression, where BIPV surfaces melts naturally with other building envelope solutions.

Climate change increases precipitation levels, stressing urban stormwater drainage systems. The laboratory is equipped with various detention systems to manage stormwater on-site before controlled release into the main drainage network.

Instruments will measure run-off volumes, allowing for tailored system combinations to local circumstances.

Building Envelope and Structure

Reducing greenhouse gas emissions often involves expanding the use of materials such as timber for building construction, especially as structural support in large buildings. Efficient and cost-optimal approaches to timber construction are in high demand. An innovative and compact timber-supported roof construction incorporating smart vapor barriers has been developed. This technique greatly reduces the risk of moisture accumulation, resulting in lower building heights, reduced materials use, an efficient construction process, and economic benefits. Properly designed and constructed buildings may also achieve robust moisture proofing, attracting significant market interest.

Furthermore, timber is proven to be beneficial to lower environmental impact of other loadbearing elements too, such as slabs, pillars, stairs, and walls,

but improved design strategies and better solutions for sound transmission in timber constructions are needed. This is crucial for the competitiveness of the timber construction sector. An acoustic timber floor without concrete topping has been developed to answer this need, using low compression mineral wool, two layers of particle board, and a floor covering overlain by massive timber elements.

Building Monitoring and User Interaction

Real-time information about building performance and user behavior is essential for continuous improvement of building operation. The laboratory is equipped with over 1500 sensors and a state-of-the-art building automation system, providing real-time data on energy use and indoor conditions. A Real-Time Locating System tracks mobile phones, enabling user interaction with the building through an app, supporting data analytics and research.

Photos: Nicola Lolli

A living laboratory

The term Living Laboratory, or Living Lab, can be used to indicate a broad spectrum of services and processes linked to research and innovation, where the focus is placed on the user and its interaction with the new ideas, technologies, and solutions, in a real-world context.

These environments are physical, social, and cultural, and the interactions span a wide range of applications. Living labs offer unique opportunities for interdisciplinary research on complex issues and transition processes, where humanities and aesthetic disciplines collaborate with technological and natural sciences. Key themes explored through living labs encompass technologies, services, and processes aimed at the green transition, healthcare and lifestyles, social inclusion, and active participation in decision-making. They are particularly well-suited for research on topics where buildings, built environments, infrastructure, cities, neighborhoods, and rural areas play a significant role.

Living labs can be categorized based on various factors. Common types of living labs have been classified in terms of driving actor (Utilizer-driven living labs, Enabler-driven living labs, Provider-driven living labs, User-driven living labs) and the primary focus of their activities (for example, Urban living labs, Rural living labs, Testbed extension living labs, and Context research and Co-creation living labs).

At the European level, the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) has mapped nearly 500 Living Labs, primarily initiated and operated by universities and research institutes, many functioning as permanent research infrastructures.

The ZEB Laboratory is an enabler-driven, testbed extension living lab that aims at addressing multidisciplinary, complex problems linked to design and operation of sustainable building technologies, building services, and building management systems. With the goal of minimizing the building's environmental impact and maximizing the user wellbeing and experience in buildings in the context of digitalization and climate change, the ZEB Laboratory lab supports research and innovation activities through:

- **Real-world testing:** innovations are tested in the real-life environment of a mixed office and education building, ensuring practicality and effectiveness.
- **User involvement:** innovations are tested by including users in the experiments, ensuring that the end products meet actual needs and preferences.
- **Laboratory grade methods:** innovations' effects are measured in both quantitative and qualitative forms through data acquisition systems and data processing techniques that ensure high-fidelity results.
- **Collaboration:** innovations are co-developed by researchers and stakeholders, with the support of researchers and technical staff at both NTNU and SINTEF, leading to more holistic and sustainable solutions.

The ZEB Laboratory complements the research infrastructure portfolio of NTNU and SINTEF by expanding the conventional laboratory-level testing infrastructure that the two institutions operate. Building technology innovations can then be tested from material-scale to full-scale prototype, and up to their interaction with the users. Services and digital solutions can be developed and demonstrated in a real-building setting with state-of-the-art infrastructure that is used in everyday life.

Photos: Nicola Lolli

Testing areas

All the four floors of the ZEB Laboratory are available arenas for experiments that investigate users' behavior and their interaction with buildings and building systems. The different areas allow experiments to be carried out considering different functions and under different scenarios, such as teaching settings and general dissemination or large gatherings settings on the 1st and on the 4th floor, and landscape office settings and meeting rooms areas on the 2nd and 3rd floor.

In addition to the extensive monitoring systems for energy flows and indoor environmental quality, the building is equipped with a sensing infrastructure that can monitor user's position thanks to mobile phones or ad-hoc badges. Through mobile phones, users can interact with the building's setting in a flexible way, and a certain degree of control over some functions of the buildings (for example lighting, daylighting, window's opening) can be adjusted to suit the experimental needs. Moreover, all the areas of the building can be independently adjusted, within a relatively large range of indoor environmental settings and setpoints, for experimental purposes.

Furthermore, one unique possibility is offered by two identical spaces, called "Twin rooms", located on the south-exposed part of the 2nd floor. These two office spaces, with a surface of around 50 m2 each, can be easily decoupled by the normal operation of the entire building, and run in more experimental modes. These rooms are equipped with additional, laboratory grade sensing technology

Technical rooms for testing of building energy and indoor environmental systems. Photo: Nicola Lolli

that enable longitudinal studies with high accuracy data collection.

Experiments on building services, energy use, indoor environmental quality, and user interactions, are also possible in a comparative form in the Twins room, leveraging the fact that two identical spaces are subject to the same boundary conditions. It can also be mentioned that part of the façade of the Twins room can be rebuilt for experiments on building envelope systems, and in particular for windows and attachments.

To complete the portfolio of areas dedicated to laboratory functions in the ZEB Lab, three technical rooms located on the 1st floor and on the 4th

floor hosts the heating, ventilation, and energy generation infrastructure of the building. Through the permanent installations in the building, a certain level of flexibility in the systems and automation for indoor environmental control, energy conversion and storage is available, and can be exploited for testing of equipment and experiments on their interaction with control systems and routines. While these systems are fully equipped with a complete data acquisition system, integrated with the combined building monitoring and automation system, additional sensors can easily be added to expand the range of measured quantities and points, either as stand-alone data acquisition system, or fully integrated with the building management system.

Twin room for detailed energy and indoor environmental quality studies with user involvement. Photo: Nicola Lolli

Data service architecture

From the first day of operation, significant efforts have been dedicated to developing and integrating digital solutions for the daily operation of the ZEB Laboratory, in its dual function as a mixed-use building and a research infrastructure. These activities aim to automate as many tasks as possible, starting from data gathering, organizing and structuring measurement data via data preparation pipelines, making data available through a service architecture platform, and ultimately analysing, visualising, and utilising the measurement data to develop data-driven service

To develop, validate, and demonstrate control algorithms that can manage technical systems in a more data-driven manner, the ZEB Laboratory is equipped with two systems: one for reading

Building management system and monitoring system at the ZEB Laboratory

measurement data from BACnet and another for writing signals back to respective BACnet points. Additionally, the laboratory features a Siemens DesignoCC Building Management System (BMS) and a service architecture solution.

Measurement data is collected from the building network (BACnet) and transferred to InfluxDB via a gateway server using the custom, in-house-developed "BACnet2Influx". InfluxDB is used to store measurement data from the ZEB Laboratory, including data from local weather stations, web services, and other third-party equipment. InfluxDB offers real-time data collection, storage, and visualisation via an API. Data in InfluxDB is organised into "buckets and measurements" accessible through an online graphical interface.

Storing data in InfluxDB facilitates trend analysis, anomaly detection, and optimisation of building operations by grouping and processing data using Flux queries and batch processing techniques. Integration with visualisation tools such as Grafana enhances this solution by enabling the creation of dashboards that provide real-time insights into building performance, energy usage, and the health of various systems, offering a comprehensive view of the facility.

The ZEB Laboratory can operate in either business-as-usual mode using the Siemens BMS or in "research mode". Scripts containing various data-driven applications related to the ZEB Laboratory, such as control of solar shading devices, the

ventilation system, or the heating system, can be used to write supervisory control rules to the actuators via BACforsk (BACØ).

BACforsk is a custom-made framework that allows for the overwriting of normal runtime routines of the BACnet at the ZEB Laboratory. The primary goal of this program is to facilitate the easy implementation of control scripts in research mode. All output values written by BACforsk have a higher priority than those written by the Siemens DesignoCC BMS, thus overwriting and disabling some of the normal runtime routines.

The ZEB Laboratory is also working to further facilitate data access for developers and researchers on other platforms. Using a lightweight public MQTT

broker, users can subscribe to and publish data to the building using their programming language of choice. This capability supports a wide range of applications, from running model-based controls anywhere in the world to displaying data in Building Information Models (BIMs) and exploring data visualisations and reporting tools.

Data service architecture for the ZEB Laboratory. Credits: Thomas Elvrum Lassen

Co-creation and dissemination space

Before the ZEB Laboratory existed as a physical space, its role as a hub for co-creation and knowledge dissemination had already begun. As an example of a building design process requiring early stakeholder engagement, students from several NTNU faculties participated in shaping the ZEB Laboratory. This process started in autumn 2016 with students from the course TBA4171 "Building and Material Engineering, Advanced Course" to test and demonstrate that the ZEB-COM targets could be met within the framework of the ZEB Laboratory concept. The "Big-room" concept was developed and refined well before its real implementation in the ICE process, through the course TBA4855 "EIT-Experts in Teamwork - Smart Building" in spring 2016.

Student involvement continued throughout the entire process until post-occupancy evaluation, covering a broad range of areas. For example, colour, light, and building accessibility for visually impaired users were addressed in the course AAR4620 "Architectural Design with Light and Colours", with a jury lead by a visually impaired researcher. This ensured that the solutions implemented were inclusive and effective, while also providing students with invaluable learning experience linked to real-world challenges.

Altogether, 35 courses contributed to the development of the ZEB Laboratory, engaging over 2200 students and producing 18 master's theses

Mentorship in action during the construction of the ZEB Laboratory: experienced professionals and apprentices collaborated on zero-emission building techniques. Photo: Veidekke

centred around the project. The ZEB Laboratory's role in educating future professionals remains ongoing, with multiple courses utilising the laboratory and its spaces for lectures, activities, and site visits. In the last academic year alone, 11 university courses have benefited from this unique educational tool.

Educational activities extend beyond university education, encompassing both younger and experienced professionals. During the construction

The knowledge centre, located on the 4th floor of the ZEB Laboratory is one of the spaces used for knowledge co-creation and dissemination. Photo: Nicola Lolli

phase, the ZEB Laboratory's role in active learning was demonstrated through the engagement of apprentices from various professions, who cumulatively contributed about one-fifth of the total work efforts in building the facility. This commitment continues today through the use of the ZEB Laboratory in continuing education and professional development activities. A significant role is played by guided tours tailored to professional audiences, featuring "hands-on" demonstrations of several laboratory features. The building's technical infrastructure, designed to be easily accessible and turned "inside-out" to facilitate knowledge dissemination, is crucial in fulfilling its role as a knowledge hub.

The ZEB Laboratory continuously hosts research project meetings, workshops, and consortium gatherings for multinational research projects where NTNU and SINTEF are partners. These events enable participants to experience high-

quality spaces and gain first-hand insights into the knowledge generated and ongoing research at the laboratory. By involving participants from outside Norway, the ZEB Laboratory enhances its role as an international infrastructure, thereby aiming to have a global impact on sustainable building practices.

Knowledge dissemination extends beyond the physical space of the ZEB Laboratory, allowing global access. The laboratory has its own "Wiki" page, accessible at wiki.zeblab.no, which serves as a portal to technical information about the building, its design, operations, and real-time data. Continuous data streams from the laboratory can be accessed through dashboards available at data.zeblab.no. These online resources ensure that the knowledge generated at the ZEB Laboratory is widely accessible and can be utilised by students, researchers, and professionals.

Community engagement space

In its role as a hub for innovation and sustainability, the ZEB Laboratory also serves as a vibrant community activity centre. The laboratory is dedicated to sharing knowledge and inspiring future generations through numerous hands-on and educational activities.

Schools and pupils are invited to explore the facility through guided tours and engaging activities. These tours offer students a unique opportunity to witness firsthand the research areas and sustainable practices and technologies employed within. Engaging young minds with the laboratory's spaces aims to spark curiosity and passion for science, technology, engineering, and architecture. During these tours, discussions also focus on the laboratory's impact on reducing carbon footprints and promoting green practices, providing both students and adult audiences with valuable insights into sustainable living.

Participation in events such as the European Researchers' Night and other art and science festivals at NTNU and in Trondheim further extends the laboratory's outreach. These events provide the public, from high-school students to the general audience, with opportunities to explore the challenges and solutions for creating a more sustainable built environment. Interactive demonstrations at these events make science accessible and engaging, fostering a deeper understanding of sustainability issues.

The common spaces within the laboratory serve as a versatile venue for a wide range of events and gatherings. Various groups, student associations, and organizations use the space for meetings, workshops, and social gatherings. This diversity of use allows a broader audience to experience the unique environment and see how being a zero-emission building with high architectural and indoor environmental quality demonstrates that sustainable transition can coexist with pleasant and livable spaces.

Regular workshops and meetings with staff from different ministries, state, and local agencies are also hosted here. These collaborations are crucial for broadly communicating research developments and supporting national and regional sustainability objectives. By reflecting and demonstrating how the laboratory's technologies, practices, and methods can be adopted by society at large, these interactions help bridge the gap between research and practical implementation, ensuring that innovative solutions reach the wider community.

At the heart of the laboratory's mission is its role as a lighthouse for sustainable transition. The facility exemplifies how innovative research and community engagement can address pressing environmental challenges. By opening its doors to the community and fostering a collaborative spirit, the ZEB Laboratory leads the way towards a more sustainable future while making science and technology accessible and exciting for all.

Photo: Gabriele Lobaccaro

Collaboration opportunities at the ZEB Laboratory

At ZEB Laboratory, we offer a range of services to support research, development, innovation, professional growth, and dissemination. Our offerings include access to extensive data sets, a full-scale testbed for smart building solutions with user involvement, and specialized courses, training sessions, and site visits.

Leveraging our comprehensive measurement data infrastructure, we help you achieve your research and innovation goals by turning data into actionable insights. Our dataset for normal building operations, available as both historical time series and real-time data, is accessible through our API. Academic partners can request free access to various datasets for developing teaching materials, problem-based assignments, and topics for bachelor's or master's theses. Industrial partners can request tailored datasets to support their projects in areas such as performance monitoring, energy management, predictive maintenance and fault detection, regulatory compliance, model development and calibration, and indoor environmental quality.

Beyond data streams from everyday operations, the ZEB Laboratory supports the implementation of new building technologies and services that require validation in a living laboratory setting. Research areas within the laboratory can be reserved and customized to investigate user-centered questions and systems. In "research mode," the laboratory

enables precise tests and experiments on its subsystems and smaller areas, allowing for the override of conventional controls to test advanced smart-building applications. Our staff at NTNU and SINTEF are well-equipped to support research and development tasks for products and services using the ZEB Laboratory's testbed functions, either through commissioned research or collaborative projects funded by national and international research grants.

We also offer supplementary services to our academic and industrial partners, including guided tours, training sessions, and dissemination events. These services utilize the ZEB Laboratory as both a venue and a case study, covering topics such as energy and environmental systems, building technologies and processes, indoor environmental quality, circular economy, zero-emission buildings, climate adaptation, and data infrastructure for smart buildings.

We invite you to explore how ZEB Laboratory can support your research, development, and innovation needs. For more information on our services and how we can collaborate, please reach out to one of our contacts on the next page.

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Photo: Nicola Lolli

Research Highlights

A glimpse into our 2024 research

The rapid advancement of digital technologies, both in hardware and software, is crucial in the transition to a sustainable built environment. This progress is evident in various initiatives at the ZEB Laboratory in 2024, where research and innovation harness advanced technologies and automation to create the knowledge and tools needed for intelligent, efficient, and sustainable buildings and cities.

Through a mix of theoretical frameworks, simulation-based studies, and laboratory-scale experiments, researchers have gained valuable insights into how advanced concepts and technologies can optimize building operations, enhance occupant satisfaction, and secure minimal environmental impact.

However, translating these concepts into practical, real-world applications remains a challenge. Buildings in real-world settings often present complexities and uncertainties that cannot be fully captured in simulation models or controlled laboratory conditions. This necessitates a shift toward practical experimentation and validation at an early stage of technology development. Living labs offer a unique opportunity to test and refine innovations in authentic building environments, bridging the gap between theoretical research and real-world application.

In the ZEB Laboratory, researchers at NTNU and SINTEF are leveraging the living lab features to generate knowledge, develop technology, and drive sustainable solutions across multiple domains. Foundational research activities carried out in 2024 include essential monitoring and data collection, which provide continuous insights into energy consumption in building operations, helping to identify baseline performance and areas for improvement. Building on this, AI-driven tools make data more accessible, such as through a chatbot interface that allows users to interact directly with building data using natural language. In parallel, advanced visualization techniques—such as interactive dashboards and augmented reality—make data more comprehensible and actionable. With augmented reality, building models with varying levels of information can be visualized, blending virtual data with the physical world for a richer, more interactive experience.

Moving from data collection to action, automated analysis tools, like real-time anomaly detection, identify performance issues early and enable swift responses, ensuring buildings maintain optimal operation. Insights from this monitoring then inform advanced control applications, including intelligent heating, ventilation, and building climatization strategies that dynamically adjust to environmental changes to maintain occupant comfort while optimizing energy use.

Research at the ZEB Laboratory also extends beyond individual buildings to encompass broader applications such as urban planning and environmental monitoring. Digital tools are applied at the city level to manage resources sustainably, creating interconnected systems that bring sustainable practices from single buildings to entire urban areas.

Each of these research activities reflects NTNU and SINTEF's commitment to advancing sustainable building technologies. Together, these initiatives demonstrate the crucial role digital tools play in fostering a more sustainable built environment. Detailed descriptions of these projects, presented in the following pages, highlight ZEB Laboratory's capabilities to enhance sustainability in buildings and cities. Sincere thanks are extended to the researchers whose efforts have made these advancements possible.

*Francesco Goia, NTNU
Knut Nordanger, SINTEF Community
John Clauss, SINTEF Community*

*Art by Ingrid Becker
Photo by Grethe Fredriksen*

Following energy use in building operation

New buildings often require lengthy commissioning to identify and resolve issues, which can take months or years. Integrating monitoring data with models based on as-built documentation could help achieve optimal performance more quickly.

Kristian Skeie works as a Research Scientist at SINTEF Community, specializing in energy efficiency and climate adaptation. His work includes utilizing data for enhancing building design and operation.

This research activity has been supported by the Research Council of Norway through the research grant nr. 257660 for The Research Centre on Zero Emission Neighbourhoods in Smart Cities.

Optimizing Building Performance with Data

Ensuring that building systems function as planned is essential for optimizing operations with data-driven services. However, data-driven models that accurately represent the current state or predict a building's energy use may not suffice to verify actual performance, adherence to design intentions, and the validity of assumptions made during the design and engineering phases. For these applications, models must possess physically interpretable attributes that establish a performance benchmark and provide actionable insights for operational improvements. At the ZEB Laboratory, we have developed and tested a simple building energy model framework informed by as-built design

Mapping of electricity sub-meters to functions and spaces

documentation and found it to have numerous applications, among them more informed understanding of building operations and building performance gap.

Deploying models for real-time energy evaluations

One advantage of this modeling framework, based on recent standards for building engineering calculations, is that it does not require data for model training but can still utilize data for calibration. The framework relies on building envelope and manufacturing data as input, which can be sourced from reports generated during building code compliance or energy labeling evaluations. Open data can also provide information about the surroundings, such as shading of building façades. Additionally, further manufacturing data is necessary to model the heat pumps and photovoltaic panels in compliance with NSPEK 3031:2023. This approach results in a more precise and dynamic representation of energy supply. Moreover, transitioning from net to gross energy demand calculations, as specified in NSPEK, is essential for making meaningful comparisons with real-time measurements.

Application of the model in the ZEB Laboratory

The availability of data on various building processes significantly affects the ability to identify performance gaps. In the ZEB Laboratory, several sub-meters monitor energy flows for different purposes. Understanding the specific measurements of each sub-meter is crucial for accurately representing detailed building consumption. This information can be encapsulated as tags in the time-series database. As shown in the flow diagram, some meters are placed on the same circuits, complicating data processing, especially when one meter is missing data for a period. Graph

Framework for models guided by as-built documentation to achieve alignment with operational data.

models may be well-suited for representing this relational hierarchy of meters (or other sensors and the spaces they serve). Future work will focus on methods for representing and validating this information, which is essential for transferring this approach to other buildings. The as-built model, executed on actual weather data, has been used to detect faults and systematically target areas for improvement. Furthermore, the framework has shown promise in predicting energy production and demand for the following day when actual loads and setpoints are used as input. These capabilities can be studied further to optimize operational strategies.

Skeie, K. (2023). Connected heat pumps in building operation – Zeb Laboratory. In Jentsch, J. (Ed.), *IEA HPT Annex 56 Digitalization and IoT for Heat Pumps – Task 2: Interfaces and platforms*.

Skeie, K., & Gustavsen, A. (2022). Building energy performance evaluation of a Norwegian single-family house applying ISO-52016. *BuildSim Nordic 2022*.

Enhancing building data accessibility

Operational data from building management systems can enhance performance when easily accessible and comprehensible. A chatbot powered by Large Language Models like ChatGPT, facilitates this by providing intuitive interactions for users to retrieve and understand the data.

Knut Nordanger works as a Senior Advisor at SINTEF Community, focusing on developing innovative data-driven applications for the building and construction industry.

This research activity has been supported by SINTEF through a strategically self-funded project, grant SEP 2024 nr. 87.

Enhancing accessibility to building management data

Building management systems generate vast amounts of data that provide valuable insights into building performance. However, accessing and interpreting this data often requires specialized technical knowledge, such as programming expertise. Reliance on traditional database interfaces and query languages increases dependence on technical staff and can lead to underutilized data resources.

Recent advances in artificial intelligence offer promising solutions to these accessibility challenges, potentially expanding the user group that can leverage data. Large Language Models (LLMs) lower

Chatbot screenshot

technical barriers by processing natural language queries, allowing users to interact with data using everyday language instead of complex query languages.

Knowledge graph extract for room sensor

A natural language chatbot for interacting with building data

To test and demonstrate how LLMs can improve accessibility to building management data, a chatbot utilizing OpenAI's GPT-4 LLM is being developed. The chatbot can handle metadata inquiries, data queries, and data retrieval. For metadata inquiries, questions about equipment and components, such as "What components are located in room 3.12?", will result in a list of components. For data queries, simple data-related questions like "What is the current temperature in room 3.18?" will provide a textual answer. Finally, for data retrieval, requests for specific data, such as "Provide all temperature data for the last three hours in room 3.21", will prepare a downloadable CSV file.

The technical foundation of the chatbot relies on organizing metadata into a knowledge graph stored in the Neo4j graph database. This graph includes entities such as systems, components, and quantities, with relationships indicating logical connections. To enhance metadata structure and improve interoperability, ontologies like Brick and SAREF provide common vocabularies and semantic structure for describing building systems and IoT devices, enabling more accurate, context-aware responses and improving chatbot scalability. When a user asks a question, the chatbot queries the graph to find the relevant metadata.

For example, it determines how the "outside temperature" is represented in the database. If the question requires data retrieval, the chatbot uses the metadata to automatically generate a query for the time series data stored in the database, processes the results, and provides a textual answer or a downloadable file.

Implementation and validation at the ZEB Laboratory

The ZEB Laboratory's state-of-the-art data infrastructure has been essential for developing the chatbot, providing a robust platform for collecting, storing, and managing real-time data from building systems and sensors. This infrastructure enabled development in a controlled environment that mimics real-world conditions, ensuring an effective, user-friendly solution capable of handling complex datasets.

Currently, the ZEB Laboratory chatbot helps researchers access data efficiently using natural language instead of the InfluxDB's Flux query language, reducing reliance on lab technicians for retrieving data, and promoting a wider usage of the ZEB Laboratory data.

Balaji, B., Bhattacharya, A., Fierro, G., Gao, J., Gluck, J., Hong, D., Johansen, A., Koh, J., Ploennigs, J., Agarwal, Y., Berges, M., Culler, D., Gupta, R., Kjærsgaard, M. B., & Srivastava, M. (2018). Brick: Metadata schema for portable smart building applications. *Applied Energy*, 226, 1273–1292.

Fan, L., Lafia, S., Li, L., Yang, F., & Hemphill, L. (2023). DataChat: Prototyping a conversational agent for dataset search and visualization. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.18358*.

García-Castro, R., Lefrançois, M., Poveda-Villalón, M., & Daniele, L. (2023). The ETSI SAREF ontology for smart applications: A long path of development and evolution. In L. Daniele, F. den Hartog, & J. Roes (Eds.), *Energy Smart Appliances: Applications, Methodologies, and Challenges* (pp. 183–215). Wiley-IEEE Press.

Interactive visualization of real-time energy data

The large amounts of data collected from buildings must be presented in a way that is useful and easy to use for experts and the general public. Interaction visualization, allowing for comparison against models, may provide a suitable solution to this need.

Stian Nyblom completed a M. Sc. degree in Computer Science at NTNU during the Spring of 2024, specializing in software engineering. He currently works as an IT consultant at Bekk Consulting.

This research activity has been supported by the Research Council of Norway through the research grant nr. 257660 for The Research Centre on Zero Emission Neighbourhoods in Smart Cities.

Maximizing building data for all audiences

The extensive sensor networks in modern buildings generate vast real-time data on system performance. This data is invaluable for professionals like architects, engineers, facility managers, urban planners, and researchers, supporting continuous assessment, maintenance, and future design. However, these data streams can also engage a broader audience. By showcasing the benefits and functioning of advanced buildings, real-time data can educate students and the general public about sustainable building technologies and performance.

While data visualization and querying solutions are well-developed for professionals, making this

data accessible to non-experts can be challenging. Interactive data visualization solutions are crucial as they make complex information more engaging and understandable, allowing non-experts to explore data at their own pace. These interactive features can also benefit experts by enabling deeper data exploration and analysis.

Developing solutions for non-expert audiences is essential for maximizing the impact and utility of building data, especially in demonstration and pilot projects.

An interactive visualization dashboard prototype

A prototype was developed to address this challenge, resulting in an interactive dashboard

Interactive visualization of the monthly energy balance over one year of operation.

that provides a high-level overview of data related to energy and greenhouse gas emissions. It also allows users to delve deeper into the data for more detailed insights. The dashboard displays both expected and actual performance values, enabling a quick comparison of the building's actual performance against simulations made during its design phase. Real-time simulations or pre-calculated simulations using historical data are employed to compare measured data with expected performance. This is facilitated by InfluxDB, which stores simulation outputs as time series alongside corresponding experimental data. The prototype features a React-based frontend, offering flexibility to adjust any aspect of the dashboard, and a custom Flask API for powerful data transformation of sensor data stored in InfluxDB, a time series database. This combination proved superior to other dedicated dashboard tools like Streamlit and Grafana, which were considered too inflexible for this task.

Leveraging time series databases for extensive visualization capabilities

The data architecture of the ZEB Laboratory enables easy retrieval and analysis of real-time measurements and simulations, crucial for the prototype's development. The extensive sensor

Interactive visualization of the energy in and out of the ZEB Laboratory for one year of operation.

network provides diverse data types, and the large data volume allows for various visualizations. A flexible time series database facilitates storing and retrieving both experimental and simulation data, enabling comparisons between actual and predicted performance.

To evaluate the dashboard's usability, surveys based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the System Usability Scale (SUS) were conducted engaging researchers from SINTEF (representing experts) and first-year architecture students (representing non-experts). Both groups found the prototype useful and easy to use, but researchers noted that additional charts and data are needed to fully meet their work-related needs, should this visualization be used in their daily activities.

Contreras-Figueroa, V., et al. (2021). Information visualization in adaptable dashboards for smart cities: A systematic review. In 2021 9th International Conference in Software Engineering Research and Innovation (CONISOFT) (pp. 34–43).

Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. MIS Quarterly, 13(3), 319–340.

Wiberg, A. H., et al. (2019). Visualisation of KPIs in zero emission neighbourhoods for improved stakeholder participation using Virtual Reality. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, 323(1), 012074.

Visualizing discipline-specific IFC files in buildings with Augmented Reality (AR)

Engaging various building users and providing effective decision-support tools can be challenging. Augmented Reality (AR) can address this by overlaying digital information onto the real world, enhancing decision-making through interactivity.

Wojciech Teclaw works as a M. Sc. at SINTEF Community and is a PhD student at NTNU. His expertise lies in the dynamic domain of BIM, supported by a strong understanding of semantics and graph databases.

This research activity has been supported through an internship from OTH Regensburg University.

From blueprints to digital reality

Traditionally, the construction industry has relied on blueprints, models, and 2D drawings for project design and execution. However, these tools fall short in visualization and collaboration, especially during the operational phase of buildings. As construction technology evolves, augmented reality (AR) is emerging as a transformative tool enabling real-time visualization by overlaying digital models onto physical spaces, greatly enhancing project planning, execution, and building operations.

Preparation of the digital layers of information

To effectively implement AR technology, proper digital infrastructure is essential. A key distinction

between 3D modeling and Building Information Modeling (BIM) is the naming convention, which allows stakeholders to do more than visually inspect a file. It enables efficient selection, capture, and management of data throughout a building project's lifecycle. This systematic approach improves collaboration and coordination, ensuring information is consistently organized and accessible. The naming convention principles are reflected in BIM models for architectural and HVAC domains. Both models have been created using Autodesk Revit and coordinated with Autodesk Navisworks to ensure they are clash-free. The naming convention standard is designed to be easily expandable and applicable to other domains. For example, the

Coordination view of ZEB Laboratory including Architecture and Ventilation domains

code AC_WD_SGL means architecture scope (AC), windows (WD), and single glass window (SGL).

AR integration in ZEB Laboratory

ZEB Laboratory uses the Gamma AR product suite to enable AR visualization of hidden (typically HVAC systems) and visible (typically architectural elements) components. IFC models of the building were uploaded to the portal, processed, and downloaded onto the Gamma AR app. On-site, users overlay these digital models onto the physical space, making hidden elements visible through their devices. This enables the identification of discrepancies, documentation of issues, and management of RFIs (Request for Information) directly within the app. Implementing AR solutions for visualizing hidden building elements offers several benefits during the operational phase. It enhances maintenance by allowing asset management teams to locate and assess building systems without invasive procedures, reducing downtime and damage. Inspections become more accurate as inspectors can see behind walls and ceilings, ensuring all

systems are correctly installed and maintained. Efficient problem-solving is facilitated by quickly identifying issues in hidden systems, leading to faster resolutions and minimal disruptions. AR serves as a powerful training tool for maintenance staff, showing exact locations and configurations of hidden elements and acting as a living document that updates with changes over the building's lifecycle. Additionally, visualizing and documenting hidden elements enhances communication between on-site staff and off-site management, ensuring a clear understanding of the building's condition and any issues. This brings transparency and precision to building operations, significantly improving maintenance efficiency and overall facility management.

Borrmann, A., König, M., Koch, C., & Beetz, J. (2018). Building Information Modeling: Why? What? How? In A. Borrmann, M. König, C. Koch, & J. Beetz (Eds.), *Building Information Modeling* (pp. 1–24). Springer International Publishing.

User interface view in Gamma AR application, displaying ventilation components hidden above the acoustic ceiling tiles in ZEB Laboratory

Anomaly detection in building operation

Efficient building automation requires quick, accurate anomaly detection for proactive maintenance, energy savings, and occupant comfort. New systems that promptly identify and address issues can prevent inefficiencies, reduce costs, and ensure occupant well-being.

This research activity has been supported through SINTEF's corporate digitalization initiative "KS Digitalisering".

Challenges in building system monitoring

Anomaly detection in building automation systems is vital for modern operations. As buildings become more complex and automated, quickly identifying and addressing system abnormalities is crucial for maintaining energy efficiency, occupant comfort, and optimizing performance. Traditional monitoring often struggles with real-time analysis and user accessibility, hindering effective maintenance and optimization in smart buildings. Operators frequently face challenges in distinguishing between normal variations and genuine anomalies, leading to delayed responses and missed energy optimization opportunities. Manual monitoring is time-consuming and prone to human error, while existing automated solutions often generate excessive false alarms, overwhelming maintenance teams.

Luis Caetano works as Senior Advisor at SINTEF Community focusing on developing data-driven applications to promote a more sustainable built environment.

Reidar Kind works as Senior Advisor at SINTEF Community focusing on implementing data-driven applications for improved building operation.

Web application for real-time analysis

Our research focused on developing a web application for real-time data stream analysis from buildings' sensors and devices. The application combines advanced anomaly detection algorithms with an intuitive user interface, providing a streamlined tool for anomaly monitoring. It detects abnormal patterns and potential issues early, thus enabling proactive maintenance and system optimization.

The anomaly detection web app serves as an initial data quality assessment and supports ZEB Laboratory operations in setting up mitigation measures to correct possible failures. These detection results can form the foundation for developing more sophisticated fault diagnosis processes. To ensure comprehensive anomaly identification, the application implements three complementary detection approaches. The first method uses statistical Z-score analysis, measuring deviations from mean behaviour using standard deviation thresholds. The second approach employs DBSCAN clustering to identify outliers based on spatial density patterns in the data. The third method uses a Special Isolation Forest algorithm, specifically adapted for time-series data, which excels at detecting temporal anomalies through random point isolation. This combination enables the effective identification of statistical deviations, cluster-based anomalies, and temporal pattern irregularities across the building systems.

Showcasing the Web application in the ZEB Laboratory

The ZEB Laboratory enabled this research by providing a robust platform for real-time data collection and analysis through its extensive network of sensors and devices. The laboratory facilitated the testing and validation of anomaly detection

methods, focusing on the performance of a heat pump's Coefficient of Performance (COP). The heat pump system was selected as a primary test case due to its critical role in building energy efficiency and its complex operational patterns that make traditional monitoring approaches insufficient. The implementation demonstrated the effectiveness of the detection methods through the web app interface, providing results for the heat pump COP time-series. The system identified anomalies where values fell below 0 or exceeded 5, aligning with theoretical expectations as the COP should remain non-negative and not exceed the maximum theoretical COP. The laboratory's sophisticated infrastructure was essential for refining both the detection algorithms and user interface to meet operational requirements.

Clauß, J., Lassen, T., Skeie, K., Andersen, K., Caetano, L., & Sartori, I. (2024). Preparing buildings for data-driven operation – Examples from the ZEB Laboratory. (Under review).

Katipamula, S., & Kim, W. (2018). A review of fault detection and diagnostics methods for building systems. *Science and Technology for the Built Environment*, 24(1), 3–21.

Web-app architecture.

Auto-tuning schemes for model-based control of room's thermal dynamics

Advanced model-based approaches require extensive development and tuning. Integrating adaptive features with real-time data enables ready-to-use models, reducing barriers to implementing model-based controls.

Marius Bagle is a MSc at SINTEF Community and a PhD candidate at NTNU, with a background in electrical engineering. His research focuses on developing methods for model-based control of building's energy systems that leverage adaptive features.

This research activity has been supported by the Research Council of Norway through the research grant nr. 257660 for The Research Centre on Zero Emission Neighbourhoods in Smart Cities.

Model-based controls' scalability challenges

Advanced control technologies, such as model predictive control, have proven effective in enhancing building energy efficiency by enabling near-optimal use of renewable energy resources and increasing the ability of buildings to adapt flexibly to intermittent energy supply. However, implementing systems that support advanced control strategies involves significant development costs related to model creation, and the tuning of controllers and state estimators. Paradoxically, this can lead to considerable energy costs during the initial phase of the system. Standard procedures for model identification include an energy-intensive test period with

constraints on occupancy, necessary to develop a suitable model of building thermal dynamics.

Control-oriented modeling of room's thermal dynamics

The hypothesis for ongoing model identification work is that high-quality, real-time operational data and prior physical knowledge can produce gray-box models suitable for control applications. This approach eliminates the need for an expensive test period and could facilitate wider adoption of predictive control technologies, significantly reducing implementation costs for room-level controls and leading to substantial energy savings.

Functioning principle of the new auto-tuning scheme

The novel identification scheme proposed has been developed to directly estimate the impact of occupancy, ventilation, and internal gains. It includes time-varying elements to account for unobservable and uncontrollable inputs, such as window and door openings. This new approach identifies a set of thermal parameters for occupied hours (which are largely influenced by occupancy and associated unobservable, user-driven phenomena) and another set of the same thermal properties for unoccupied hours (primarily used to track indoor temperature and build a filtering history to estimate unobserved temperatures, such as the envelope temperature). In addition to allowing for time-varying elements within the estimation horizon, all physical parameters are made time-varying in the sense that they are frequently (e.g. daily, but possibly even more often) identified based on an optimization problem which combines recent data and prior knowledge. This combined approach enables an

auto-tuning feature in this scheme that significantly improves the prediction performance of the model on unseen data, especially when operating conditions are changed.

API-based data pipelines for flexible workflow automation

The newly proposed identification scheme is extensively tested and validated using data from the ZEB Laboratory Twin rooms. Empirical evidence shows the scheme outperforms standard procedures, delivering parameters related to building thermal dynamics and process/measurement noise, essential for model predictive controllers. The laboratory's comprehensive measurement infrastructure, the significant amount of data available, and the presence of two similar rooms allow for easy testing of the scheme's temporal and spatial generalizability. The abundance of energy meters at the radiator string level enabled more accurate model scheme development and validation. Additionally, direct access to raw data through the dedicated API provided a significant advantage, allowing full control of the resampling process and greater workflow automation.

Blum, D. H., Arendt, K., Rivalin, L., Piette, M. A., Wetter, M., & Veje, C. T. (2019). Practical factors of envelope model setup and their effects on the performance of model predictive control for building heating, ventilating, and air conditioning systems. *Applied Energy*, 236, 410–425.

Blum, D., Wang, Z., Weyandt, C., Kim, D., Wetter, M., Hong, T., & Piette, M. A. (2024). Field demonstration and implementation analysis of model predictive control in an office HVAC system. *Applied Energy*, 318, 119104.

Drgoña, J., Arroyo, J., Cupeiro Figueroa, I., Blum, D., Arendt, K., Kim, D., Ollé, E. P., Oravec, J., Wetter, M., Vrabie, D. L., & Helsen, L. (2020). All you need to know about model predictive control for buildings. *Annual Reviews in Control*, 50, 190–232.

Enabling demand-response in building heating systems with PCM-based storage solutions

Energy flexibility in buildings is a critical resource to support the transition towards a sustainable power system with high penetration of renewables. New control algorithms are needed to harness the potential energy flexibility within building heating systems.

This research activity has been supported by the Research Council of Norway through the research grant nr. 257660 for The Research Centre on Zero Emission Neighbourhoods in Smart Cities, and by the Technical University of Denmark through the DTU Alliance PhD scholarship.

Buildings as active nodes in energy grids

Buildings are significant sources of energy flexibility for providing ancillary services to electricity or district heating grids, supporting the integration of renewable energy sources like wind and solar. Thermal Energy Storage (TES) devices within building heating systems capture and store energy during low-demand periods and release it during high-demand periods, decoupling energy demand from supply. Model Predictive Control (MPC) of TES effectively generates demand flexibility while maintaining building energy efficiency. Phase Change Materials (PCMs) are among the most mature technologies to enhance Demand Response (DR) in buildings due to their high energy storage

density, thermal stability, reliability, and economic viability.

Model-predictive control of a PCM-based TES

An optimal predictive control strategy for the PCM-based TES was developed to optimise the thermal storage capability of the PCM to shift the heating load of the building based on time-varying electricity price signals, i.e., to achieve price-based demand response. Numerical models were developed as decision support tools for the predictive controller: a nonlinear model capturing the complex dynamics of the TES and the heating system (including models for the heat pump, PCM, radiators, etc.), a prediction model providing reliable estimates of

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Schematic of the heating system of the ZEB Laboratory.

the future thermal demand (space heating), and external information such as weather forecasts and electricity price signals. An advanced nonlinear optimisation algorithm was developed to optimise the operation of the PCM TES while considering the demand requirements and boundary conditions. The research study aimed at demonstrating an advanced control strategy to intelligently manage the PCM-based TES to exhibit a high degree of demand flexibility and to provide responsive grid ancillary services through the effective use of the storage features of the thermal system. In comparison to a rule-based control, the simulated operation of the developed innovative controller transformed the heating system from an inflexible one to a highly flexible system (flexibility factor equal to 1). Storage capacity of around 100 to 120 kWh was available to be shifted based on the grid requests for up/down regulation. Energy cost and consumption were reduced by more than 80%.

Advanced building services infrastructure

The ZEB Laboratory is ideal for studying how buildings can function as active nodes in energy grids. It features innovative bio-based PCM storage, capable of storing and delivering heat

Optimised charging schedule of the PCM TES (top) and thermal energy stored and predicted energy demand (excess charging and reduced charging are in green and red, respectively) (bottom).

on-demand for space heating, domestic hot water, and ventilation. The laboratory's extensive instrumentation provides detailed insights into the thermal system's performance and status, enabling realistic model creation and facilitates calibration. Additionally, the laboratory offers a unique platform for testing advanced control algorithms in a semi-controlled, realistic, and safe environment. The controller will be demonstrated in real-time at the ZEB Laboratory, using the laboratory's data infrastructure that ensures easy integration of third-party algorithms into the building management system.

Nunna, A. C., et al. (2024). Optimal control of a bio-based phase change material thermal energy storage for demand response. *SSRN*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4894127>

Nunna, A. C., et al. (2023). Demand side flexibility for a heat booster substation with ultra low temperature district heating. *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, 36, 101185.

Ventilation control to save energy and increase comfort and productivity

Ventilation is essential for comfort, health, and productivity in buildings but significantly increases energy use. Expanding indoor air quality parameters in ventilation controls can optimize benefits without raising energy consumption.

Maria Justo Alonso works as Senior Research Scientist at SINTEF Community focusing on ventilation and heating control in buildings to reduce energy use and improve indoor air quality.

This research activity has been supported by the Research Council of Norway through the research grant nr. 257660 for The Research Centre on Zero Emission Neighbourhoods in Smart Cities, and by SINTEF through a strategically self-funded project, grant SEP 2023 nr. 70.

Current challenges in building ventilation

Policy frameworks aim to promote well-being and health by ensuring clean air, renovated energy efficient buildings, cleaner energy, and clean technological innovation. While improving building energy efficiency, we must also address the preservation of indoor air quality (IAQ) as it affects health, productivity, and well-being. Poor IAQ can trigger health issues, including allergy, respiratory problems, and decreased cognitive function. Additionally, as businesses become aware of the costs associated with decreased work efficiency and illness-related absenteeism, optimizing IAQ has gained economic significance as well.

Reduce the supplied airflow rates without affecting IAQ

The evolution of office culture, particularly the shift toward remote work, has created more variable occupancy profiles in buildings. This change has underscored the importance of demand-controlled ventilation (DCV). In the ZEB laboratory, efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from building operations led to an increase in zones controlled by single DCV dampers compared to a similar, state-of-the-art office building. This approach was based on the assumption that, with the use of low-emission materials and strategically placed IAQ sensors, airflow rates could be reduced without compromising indoor air quality. Longitudinal

tests in the laboratory's office spaces confirmed that airflow rates can indeed be reduced without increasing CO₂, PM2.5, formaldehyde, or TVOC levels, while maintaining satisfactory temperature and humidity. However, meeting rooms require careful regulation as they often exhibit the highest temperatures and CO₂ concentrations. Survey results revealed generally satisfied users, with the highest dissatisfaction and complaints were linked to thermal conditions and indoor air quality. The research showed that higher temperatures tend to lower perception of the IAQ, with 30% finding it uncomfortably warm. TVOC measurements showed little correlation with perceived odor, suggesting a need for alternative ways to measure odor. Statistical analysis revealed no significant link between most IEQ parameters and occupant satisfaction, except for the impact of temperature on IAQ and comfort.

The ZEB Laboratory as a research platform

The ZEB laboratory's unique twin room setup proved instrumental for this research, as it allowed for the examination of the effects of various air pollutants

on two highly similar populations. Notably, these tests were conducted in an indoor environment that met the general definition of good air quality, yet even at low concentrations, pollutants still demonstrated measurable effects. Further testing in the twin rooms at ZEB laboratory indicate that environmental factors like temperature, humidity, PM2.5, formaldehyde, and CO₂ levels negatively affect cognitive and motor functions. However, typical ventilation systems measure only CO₂.

Du, B., Tandoc, M. C., Mack, M. L., & Siegel, J. A. (2020). Indoor CO₂ concentrations and cognitive function: A critical review. *Indoor Air*, 30(6), 1067–1082.

Mujan, I., Anđelković, A. S., Munčan, V., Kljajić, M., & Ružić, D. (2019). Influence of indoor environmental quality on human health and productivity: A review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 217, 646–657.

Justo Alonso, M., Alonso, M. J., & Skeie, K. (2024). Air quality for various ventilation solutions in a Norwegian Zero Emission Building office. *SpliTech Conference 2024*.

Justo Alonso, M., Alonso, M. J., & Skeie, K. (2024). IAQ and ventilation measurements at the "ZEB Laboratory" office building in Norway. *Journal of Indoor Environments*.

Heat map of the environmental variables: CO₂, relative humidity (RH), temperature, formaldehyde, total volatile organic compounds (TVOC), and PM_{2.5}

Spider graph showing the impact of indoor air quality parameters on performance tests

Predicting solar accessibility in modern high-latitude cities

Uncontrolled urban growth and densification threaten solar accessibility in buildings. Reliable prediction models for high-latitudes and complete assessment processes are essential for improved solar energy planning in urban areas.

This research activity has been supported by the Research Council of Norway through the research grant nr. 324243 for the FRIPRO-FRINATEK project "HELIOS"

Challenges in high-latitude solar analysis

Accurate estimations of solar accessibility of urban surfaces are essential for planning purposes such as optimal design of photovoltaic (PV) systems, assessing the impact of new structures, and refining solar energy predictions. Photovoltaic model chains for irradiance-to-power conversion are typically used in this process. However, these models are mostly parametrized and validated for low- and mid-latitudes, with limited reliability for high-latitude (greater than 60°N) applications. High-latitude solar analyses face unique challenges due to seasonal solar radiation variability, large solar azimuth range, low solar elevation, snow deposition, and ice accretion. As Nordic cities densify and grow, reliable

tools become increasingly crucial for sustainable urban development.

Model performance variability at high latitudes

The research aimed at providing insights into the performance and reliability of different photovoltaic model chains by evaluating performance variability based on input parameters such as clearness index, sunray angle of incidence, relative airmass, and air temperature.

The research started by compiling a model library containing the most used numerical models for various steps of the photovoltaic (PV) model chain. The focus was on horizontal-to-tilted irradiance conversion to determine the best combination of

Mattia Manni is a post-doctoral researcher at NTNU specializing in solar potential analysis and photovoltaic integration at various scales to improve energy generation forecast and support grid decarbonization efforts.

Changes in the geometry model from the point cloud data to the high-LoD 3D model of the ZEB Laboratory and to the solar potential analysis.

state-of-the-art decomposition and transposition models for high-latitude applications.

The model chain was then expanded to include PV system performance simulation in urban environments, addressing shading from the urban context. A data-driven methodology combining an empirical shading mask and a modelled sky view factor was developed using Ladybug Sky Mask components.

Results of the comparison of the different model chains' outputs with experimental data from the ZEB Laboratory highlighted how the accuracy and precision of the model chains strongly depended on the surface tilt and azimuth angles. For example, the model chains that performed the best in the tilted roof (Perez2/Temps) and pergola (Perez2/Olmo2) were remarkably bad in case of vertical facades, where Perez model family outperformed the rest. Moreover, it was shown that solar modelling process during the winter months, with narrow range of solar elevation and azimuth values, may still lead to non-negligible discrepancies.

The ZEB Laboratory data mine

The ZEB Laboratory's monitoring system enables systematic comparison of experimental data with modelling outputs (irradiance and PV power). It tracks solar irradiance and PV power for different building surfaces (roof and facades) with high

temporal and spatial resolution. Multiple Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) systems on the same surface allow investigation of partial shading impacts on PV output. The extensive data collection from the same building ensures consistent boundary conditions, minimizing external variability and enhancing result reliability, as it reduces location-specific biases. Furthermore, a unique feature is the irradiance sensor and PV surface on a north-exposed façade, as solar energy can be harvested during summer from unconventional façade and roof orientations at high latitudes.

Manni, M., Jouttijärvi, S., Ranta, S., Miettunen, K., & Lobaccaro, G. (2024). Validation of model chains for global tilted irradiance on East-West vertical bifacial photovoltaics at high latitudes. *Renewable Energy*, 220, 119722.

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Solar irradiance map of the NTNU Gløshaughen campus.

Pollutants in urban runoff: Sources, monitoring, and treatment approaches

Merethe Strømberg is a PhD-candidate at NTNU, specializing in stormwater research. Her work focuses on stormwater quality and pollutants from urban surfaces, exploring implications for effective treatment.

Urban stormwater runoff introduces pollutants that degrade freshwater quality. Knowing the effectiveness of bioretention cells opens for better treatment strategies for pollutant removal.

This research activity has been supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program through the research grant nr. 101060428 for the project StopUP.

Urbanization and water quality challenges

Achieving good ecological and chemical status in water bodies is crucial for a sustainable built environment, leading to an increased focus on monitoring urban pollutants. Various urban surfaces contribute differently to pollutant loads in water runoff, including traditional pollutants like particulate matter and heavy metals, as well as emerging contaminants such as microplastics and pharmaceuticals. Although the general impact of urban stormwater on water quality is known, there remains a knowledge gap regarding the characteristics, sources, and processes of these pollutants. Some may have long-term ecological effects that are not yet fully understood. Identifying

pollution sources and understanding pollution pathways are thus essential for effective stormwater treatment strategies to maintain good water body status amid urbanization.

Innovative stormwater monitoring possibilities

In urban areas, pollutants originate from atmospheric deposition, traffic activities, and building materials, interacting differently with built and green surfaces. This complexity makes it challenging to separate the effects of various pollutant and surface combinations when monitoring in the wastewater network. Additionally, finding safe access points for monitoring is difficult in conventional stormwater systems.

Three monitored surfaces at ZEB laboratory to investigate single-source land use impact on stormwater quality.

The ZEB Laboratory's stormwater system offers distinct monitoring possibilities, combining various detention systems, including a bioretention cell, with a water detention tank designed to collect contributions from different surfaces separately. During rainfall events, stormwater from the parking lot and roof area is collected in separate inlets in the underground detention tank. This setup enables separate laboratory analyses, helping identify the effects of specific surfaces and land uses on pollutant levels and types. The ZEB Laboratory testbed, equipped with a dedicated stormwater system, electricity, and internal data loggers, provides a safe and unique monitoring infrastructure for stormwater management research.

Treating stormwater using biofilter technology

To investigate stormwater treatment strategies, the bioretention cell outside the ZEB Laboratory is used. An effective biofilter can capture pollutants before they reach water bodies by enhancing stormwater quality through filtration via engineered soil media. The performance of the bioretention cell is tested with water from the detention tank, assessing the implications of land use and rainfall patterns on contaminant removal. The treated water in this system is either infiltrated into the soil or collected by an underdrain

and discharged to the river. To assess biofilter performance, inflow and outflow samples were analysed for emerging contaminants, including polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), heavy metals (HMs), microplastics, and ecotoxicity, as well as for particle load and size changes. The biofilter shows promising results in removing particulate PAHs and HMs; however, dissolved contaminant levels often increased in the outflow. This aligns with existing research suggesting that additives in the filter media are needed to improve dissolved pollutant removal. These contaminants are also more bioavailable and therefore more ecologically impactful in receiving waters.

Blecken, G., Lange, K., Beryani, A., Furén, R., Österlund, H., Flanagan, K., & Viklander, M. (2024). Dagvattenbiofilter och regnbädder - rening och ackumulering av föroreningar (No. SVU-rapport 2024-17). Svensk Vatten.

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Müller, A., Österlund, H., Marsalek, J., & Viklander, M. (2020). The pollution conveyed by urban runoff: A review of sources. *Science of The Total Environment*, 709, 136125.

Photo: Nicola Lolli

A large, semi-transparent green number '3' is overlaid on the right side of the image. The background is a photograph of a modern interior space with light-colored wood paneling on the walls and ceiling. A staircase with wooden treads and a black metal railing is visible on the left. In the center, there is a spiral staircase with a black metal frame. A black pipe runs along the wall. A window is visible on the right wall. The overall atmosphere is bright and clean.

Factsheets

Key timeline information

Key dimensional data

Key energy and emission performance data

60.6 kWh/m²
Total specific net energy need (thermal and electric)

67.9 kWh/m²
Specific exported solar energy

16.3 kWh/m²
Specific solar energy production for own use

5.33 kgCO₂ eq/m² year
Specific emissions for materials (including replacements), for 60 years

1.20 kgCO₂ eq/m² year
Specific emissions for construction phase, for 60 years

4.73 kgCO₂ eq/m² year
Specific emissions for operation phase, for 60 years

-11.83 kgCO₂ eq/m² year
Specific avoided emissions (solar energy production) during operation phase, for 60 years

-0.57 kgCO₂ eq/m² year
Specific total emission balance (ZEB-COM), for 60 years

Key solar energy systems data

963 m²
Total PV panel surface (roof, facades, pergola)

700
Total number of PV panels

181 kW_p
Total installed capacity

5 PV
panels type

146500 kWh
Estimated yearly solar energy production

Key data on design and construction project partners

The laboratory was developed in collaboration between

The laboratory received funding from

Project management structure and roles

Art by Ingrid Becker
Photo by Grethe Fredriksen

Instagram
zeblaboratory

LinkedIn
Zero Emission
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